

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL***APOE* ε4-related differences in brain structure, function, and connectivity at midlife:****A scoping review**

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Search Strategy

Ovid MEDLINE(R) ALL <1946 to July 10, 2024>

1. apolipoprotein e/ or apolipoprotein e2/ or apolipoprotein e3/ or apolipoprotein e4/
[6874]
2. (apolipoprotein*-e* or apoe* or apo-e* or apoprotein*-e*).ti,ab,kf [39993]
3. 1 or 2 [40612]
4. functional neuroimaging/ or brain mapping/ or connectome/ or magnetic resonance
imaging/ or diffusion magnetic resonance imaging/ or diffusion tensor imaging/
[576203]
5. ((magnetic resonance adj3 (imag* or scan or scans or scanning)) or ((diffusion
weight* or diffusion tensor) adj3 (imag* or scan* or scans or scanning)) or ((mr or
nmr) adj (imag* or scan or scans or scanning)) or (((funct* or intrinsic) adj1
connect*) or mri* or fmri* or f-mri* or nmri or dmri* or d-mri* or dti or dwi or
rsfmri* or resting-state)).ti,ab,kf [632225]
6. 4 or 5 [841108]
7. 3 and 6 [2936]
8. 7 not (exp animals/ not humans.sh.) [2717]

Embase Classic+Embase <1947 to 2024 July 10>

1. apolipoprotein e/ or apolipoprotein e2/ or apolipoprotein e3/ or apolipoprotein e4/
[47664]
2. (apolipoprotein*-e* or apoe* or apo-e* or apoprotein*-e*).ti,ab,kf [56667]
3. 1 or 2 [68509]
4. functional neuroimaging/ or brain mapping/ or connectome/ or nuclear magnetic
resonance imaging/ or diffusion weighted imaging/ or diffusion tensor imaging/
[1164151]
5. ((magnetic resonance adj3 (imag* or scan or scans or scanning)) or ((diffusion
weight* or diffusion tensor) adj3 (imag* or scan* or scans or scanning)) or ((mr or
nmr) adj (imag* or scan or scans or scanning)) or (((funct* or intrinsic) adj1
connect*) or mri* or fmri* or f-mri* or nmri or dmri* or d-mri* or dti or dwi or
rsfmri* or resting-state)).ti,ab,kf [962972]
6. 4 or 5 [1403377]
7. 3 and 6 [6719]
8. 7 not ((exp animal/ or animal experiment/ or nonhuman/) not (exp human/ or human
experiment/)) [6199]

APA PsycInfo <1967 to July Week 1 2024>

1. Apolipoprotein E/ [3180]
2. (apolipoprotein*-e* or apoe* or apo-e* or apoprotein*-e*).ab,id,ti [7910]
3. 1 or 2 [7943]
4. Brain Connectivity/ or magnetic resonance imaging/ or diffusion tensor imaging/ or functional magnetic resonance imaging/ [66106]
5. ((magnetic resonance adj3 (imag* or scan or scans or scanning)) or ((diffusion weight* or diffusion tensor) adj3 (imag* or scan* or scans or scanning)) or ((mr or nmr) adj (imag* or scan or scans or scanning)) or (((funct* or intrinsic) adj1 connect*) or mri* or fmri* or f-mri* or nmri or dmri* or d-mri* or dti or dwi or rsfmri* or resting-state)).ab,id,ti [114487]
6. 4 or 5 [118226]
7. 3 and 6 [1312]

Scopus

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( TITLE-ABS ( "apolipoprotein*-e*" OR "apo-e*" OR "apoprotein*-e" ) ) AND  
( ( TITLE-ABS ( ( ( "magnetic resonance" ) W/3 ( imag* OR scan OR scans OR scanning ) )  
)) OR ( TITLE-ABS ( ( ( "diffusion weight*" OR "diffusion tensor" ) W/3 ( imag* OR scan*  
OR scans OR scanning ) ) ) ) OR ( TITLE-ABS ( ( ( mr OR nmr ) PRE/1 ( imag* OR scan  
OR scans OR scanning ) ) ) ) OR ( TITLE-ABS ( ( ( funct* OR intrinsic ) W/1 connect* ) ) )  
OR ( TITLE-ABS ( mri* OR fmri* OR "f-mri*" OR nmri OR dmri* OR "d-mri*" OR dti OR  
dwi OR rsfmri* OR "resting-state" ) ) ) )
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Age Range Analysis

During full-text screening, we excluded 62 studies for failing to report an age range. The logic behind this exclusion, outlined in our pre-registered protocol, was straightforward: means and standard deviations (or standard errors¹) do not prove conclusively that individuals younger than 40 or older than 65 were excluded from the to-be-reviewed studies. Thus, by requiring that studies report an age range, we were able to ensure that our review focused on midlife-specific differences between *APOE* ϵ 4 carriers and non-carriers. However, we acknowledge that our approach placed a greater emphasis on specificity than sensitivity and could, in some cases, lead to relevant studies being excluded for simple differences in reporting standards. As such, we re-assessed each of the 62 studies. Specifically, for each study, we extracted the groups means and standard deviations, estimated an age range using these values ($M \pm 2$ SDs), and then compared this against our pre-stated cut-offs (40-65 years). This approach relies on the assumption that age is normally distributed, something that is often difficult – if not impossible – to evaluate from the available data. Nevertheless, this approach does provide some insight as to the suitability of our approach.

Of the 62 studies examined, we found that 36 (58.1%) reported group means that were outside our pre-stated range (e.g., mean age = 75.1). A further 23 studies (37.1%) reported group means that fell within 40-65 years but, when accounting for the reported standard deviations, likely included participants below 40 or above 65 years. This left 3 studies (4.8%) whose estimated age ranges were acceptable. However, two of these studies compared “high” and “low” AD risk groups, which was defined by family history or a combination of family history and *APOE* ϵ 4 (i.e., there was no *APOE* ϵ 4 comparison). These studies, therefore, were not relevant for this scoping review. The one possible exception was Brenowitz et al. (2023).

¹ If standard errors were reported for age, we multiplied the reported values by the square root of the sample size to obtain standard deviations ($SD = SE \times \sqrt{n}$).

Technically, this study did not report the relevant figures (*Ms*, *SDs*) for *APOE* ϵ 4 carriers and non-carriers, nor for their overall MRI sample (i.e., the most relevant sample for this review). However, the full sample had a mean age of 55.5 and a standard deviation of 3.3, which is consistent with a range within 40-65 years (assuming a normal distribution for age). It is notable that this excluded study – the only one arguably consistent with our definition of midlife – also found no association between *APOE* ϵ 4 and brain health outcomes, namely total brain volume and hippocampal volume.

In sum, this supplementary analysis suggests that our pre-registered age criterion did not lead the exclusion of significant midlife-specific studies.

References

- Brenowitz, W. D., Fornage, M., Launer, L. J., Habes, M., Davatzikos, C., & Yaffe, K. (2023). Alzheimer's disease genetic risk, cognition, and brain aging in midlife. *Annals of Neurology*, 93(3), 629–634. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ana.26569>

Figures

Figure 1

Total Sample Size as a Function of Publication Year.

Note. Total sample size and publication year for midlife studies examining differences between *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ carriers and non-carriers. Each circle represents an individual study and is colored according to the neural properties examined.